

A 12.8 ka Microspherule and Nanoparticle Marker Horizon in Stratified Paleoamerican Deposits at Smith Mountain Lake (44PY152), USA

Supporting Information

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SEM and EDS Data

Image Name: smith lake_40(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.17 µm
 Acc. Voltage: 20.0 kV
 Magnification: 4894

Weight %

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_40(1)_pt1	21.92	0.37	1.13	0.16	0.24	0.19	0.72	75.26

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_40(1)_pt1	±0.31	±0.01	±0.02	±0.03	±0.03	±0.02	±0.04	±0.23

Atom %

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_40(1)_pt1	48.97	0.49	1.43	0.14	0.18	0.13	0.47	48.17

Supplementary Fig S1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Supplementary Fig S2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Supplementary Fig S3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for highly oxygen-depleted iron inclusions on an iron-rich microspherule (see Supplementary Fig S2) from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1-3).

Image Name: smith lake_22(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.07 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 20.0 kV
 Magnification: 11419

Full scale counts: 9481
 Integral Counts: 991511

smith lake_22(1)_pt1

Cursor: 0.274 keV
 11923 Counts

Weight %

	O	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_22(1)_pt1	20.16	0.83	1.38	0.10	0.12	0.71	0.17	0.68	75.84

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_22(1)_pt1	±0.23	±0.02	±0.02	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02	±0.02	±0.08	±0.24

Atom %

	O	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_22(1)_pt1	46.09	1.13	1.80	0.09	0.11	0.54	0.12	0.45	49.67

Supplementary Fig S4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: smith lake_39(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.13 µm
 Acc. Voltage: 20.0 kV
 Magnification: 6526

Weight %

	N	O	Na	Al	Si	P	S	Ca	Cr	Mn	Fe	Mo
smith lake_39(1)_pt1		20.30	1.53	0.27	0.54			0.07	0.13	0.75	76.23	0.18
smith lake_39(1)_pt2	0.00	0.00	6.78	0.26	0.52	0.09	0.06		0.16	0.90	91.23	

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	N	O	Na	Al	Si	P	S	Ca	Cr	Mn	Fe	Mo
smith lake_39(1)_pt1		±0.15	±0.03	±0.02	±0.01			±0.01	±0.02	±0.04	±0.25	±0.03
smith lake_39(1)_pt2	±0.00	±0.00	±0.08	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02		±0.03	±0.05	±0.29	

Atom %

	N	O	Na	Al	Si	P	S	Ca	Cr	Mn	Fe	Mo
smith lake_39(1)_pt1		46.14	2.43	0.36	0.70			0.06	0.09	0.50	49.65	0.07
smith lake_39(1)_pt2	0.00	0.00	14.88	0.49	0.94	0.14	0.10		0.15	0.82	82.47	

Supplementary Fig S5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1 and 2).

Image Name: smith lake_36(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.13 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 20.0 kV
 Magnification: 6526

Weight %

	O	Al	Si	P	S	Mn	Fe	Cu
smith lake_36(1)_pt1	21.94	0.31	0.55	0.05		0.39	76.75	
smith lake_36(1)_pt2	19.90	0.27	0.53		6.66	12.34	59.98	0.33

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Al	Si	P	S	Mn	Fe	Cu
smith lake_36(1)_pt1	±0.19	±0.02	±0.01	±0.01		±0.04	±0.24	
smith lake_36(1)_pt2	±0.16	±0.02	±0.01		±0.04	±0.13	±0.23	±0.06

Atom %

	O	Al	Si	P	S	Mn	Fe	Cu
smith lake_36(1)_pt1	49.23	0.41	0.71	0.06		0.26	49.33	
smith lake_36(1)_pt2	44.67	0.36	0.68		7.46	8.06	38.57	0.18

Supplementary Fig S6. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1 and 2).

Image Name: smith lake_36(2)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.13 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 30.0 kV
 Magnification: 6526

Full scale counts: 14735
 Integral Counts: 1649792
 smith lake_36(2)_pt1
 Cursor: 2.262 keV
 3373 Counts

Weight %

	O	Al	Si	S	Ca	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_36(2)_pt1	16.09	0.35	0.54	3.69	0.04	0.08	4.22	74.98

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Al	Si	S	Ca	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_36(2)_pt1	±0.94	±0.02	±0.01	±0.03	±0.01	±0.01	±0.06	±0.17

Atom %

	O	Al	Si	S	Ca	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_36(2)_pt1	39.05	0.51	0.75	4.48	0.04	0.06	2.98	52.14

Supplementary Fig S7. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: smith lake_28(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.10 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 30.0 kV
 Magnification: 8157

Full scale counts: 9672
 Integral Counts: 1772636

smith lake_28(1)_pt1

Cursor: 2.262 keV
 812 Counts

klm - 78 - Pt
 Weight %

	O	Al	Si	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_28(1)_pt1	24.58	0.47	0.41	0.11	4.92	0.31	69.20

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Al	Si	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_28(1)_pt1	±0.23	±0.01	±0.02	±0.02	±0.04	±0.05	±0.16

Atom %

	O	Al	Si	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_28(1)_pt1	52.79	0.60	0.51	0.08	3.25	0.19	42.58

Supplementary Fig S8. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a chromferrite (CrFe) microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: smith lake_22(2)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.07 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 30.0 kV
 Magnification: 11419

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Cu	Zn
<i>smith lake_22(2)_pt 1</i>	20.98	0.17	0.90	0.95		0.04	0.13	0.13	0.26	0.31	73.64	0.45	2.05
<i>smith lake_22(2)_pt 2</i>	21.99	0.15	1.73	1.18	0.25		0.12	0.12	0.25	0.61	71.30	0.37	1.94

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Cu	Zn
<i>smith lake_22(2)_pt1</i>	±0.36	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02		±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.05	±0.17	±0.03	±0.08
<i>smith lake_22(2)_pt2</i>	±0.40	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.01		±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.05	±0.17	±0.03	±0.08

Atom %

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Cu	Zn
<i>smith lake_22(2)_pt 1</i>	47.52	0.25	1.20	1.22		0.04	0.12	0.10	0.18	0.20	47.78	0.26	1.14
<i>smith lake_22(2)_pt 2</i>	48.60	0.21	2.27	1.49	0.28		0.11	0.09	0.17	0.39	45.14	0.20	1.05

Supplementary Fig S9. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1 and 2).

Supplementary Fig S10. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: smith lake_23(2)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.07 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 30.0 kV
 Magnification: 11419

Full scale counts: 4623
 Integral Counts: 450946

smith lake_23(2)_pt1

Cursor: 2.262 keV
 126 Counts

Weight %

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Zn
smith lake_23(2)_pt													
1	15.32	1.40	0.56	1.06	3.47	0.19	0.44	3.33	0.26	0.51	68.26	0.26	4.93

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Zn
smith lake_23(2)_pt1	±0.17	±0.06	±0.04	±0.03	±0.04	±0.02	±0.04	±0.06	±0.02	±0.04	±0.26	±0.05	±0.18

Atom %

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Zn
smith lake_23(2)_pt													
1	36.73	2.34	0.88	1.51	4.75	0.19	0.42	2.67	0.19	0.35	46.90	0.17	2.90

Supplementary Fig S11. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich and highly oxygen-depleted microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: smith lake_23(3)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.01 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 30.0 kV
 Magnification: 163150

Weight %

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn
<i>smith lake_23(3)_pt1</i>	11.36	0.50	1.07	2.71		0.17	0.32	2.10	0.22	0.90	71.89	8.76
<i>smith lake_23(3)_pt2</i>	14.07	0.84	1.14	2.70	0.11	0.15	0.30	2.07	0.36	1.15	68.83	8.26

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn
<i>smith lake_23(3)_pt1</i>	± 0.36	± 0.07	± 0.06	± 0.03		± 0.01	± 0.02	± 0.05	± 0.02	± 0.08	± 0.24	± 0.18
<i>smith lake_23(3)_pt2</i>	± 0.37	± 0.07	± 0.03	± 0.03	± 0.02	± 0.01	± 0.02	± 0.05	± 0.02	± 0.08	± 0.23	± 0.17

Atom %

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn
<i>smith lake_23(3)_pt1</i>	30.02	0.88	1.68	4.08		0.19	0.34	1.86	0.18	0.69	54.44	5.66
<i>smith lake_23(3)_pt2</i>	35.21	1.38	1.69	3.84	0.15	0.16	0.30	1.73	0.28	0.84	49.35	5.06

Supplementary Fig S12. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for highly oxygen-depleted FeTiZn surface inclusions on an iron-rich microspherule (see Supplementary Fig S11) from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1 and 2).

Image Name: smith lake_RTpad_43and28(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.25 µm
 Acc. Voltage: 30.0 kV
 Magnification: 3263

Weight %

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_43and28(1)_pt1	25.90	0.43	0.50	0.05	0.07	0.34	72.72
smith lake_RTpad_43and28(1)_pt2	23.43	0.40	0.47	0.08	0.06	0.28	75.28

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_43and28(1)_pt1	±0.14	±0.02	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.04	±0.16
smith lake_RTpad_43and28(1)_pt2	±0.13	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.04	±0.17

Atom %

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_43and28(1)_pt1	54.63	0.54	0.60	0.04	0.05	0.21	43.94
smith lake_RTpad_43and28(1)_pt2	51.34	0.52	0.59	0.07	0.05	0.18	47.26

Supplementary Fig S13. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for iron-rich microspherules from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1 and 2).

Image Name: smith lake_RTpad_48(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.21 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 30.0 kV
 Magnification: 3916

Weight %

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_48(1)_pt1	22.28	0.56	0.71	0.06	0.39	0.68	0.58	74.75

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_48(1)_pt1	±0.33	±0.03	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02	±0.02	±0.05	±0.16

Atom %

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_48(1)_pt1	49.56	0.73	0.90	0.06	0.29	0.46	0.37	47.63

Supplementary Fig S13. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a broken iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: smith lake_RTpad_25(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.10 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 30.0 kV
 Magnification: 8157

Weight %

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_25(1)_pt1	22.43	0.78	0.69	0.04	0.82	0.19	0.64	74.42

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_25(1)_pt1	±0.27	±0.03	±0.02	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02	±0.17

Atom %

	O	Al	Si	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith lake_RTpad_25(1)_pt1	49.68	1.02	0.87	0.04	0.61	0.13	0.41	47.23

Supplementary Fig S14. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: smth mt lake_27um_14-15cm
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.10 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 25.0 kV
 Magnification: 8157

Weight %

	C	O	F	Al	Si	P	Ti	Mn	Fe
smth mt lake_27um_14-15cm_pt1	25.91	35.72		0.18	0.11	0.03	0.12	0.32	37.61
smth mt lake_27um_14-15cm_pt2		28.94	0.00	0.29	0.24			0.56	69.96

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	C	O	F	Al	Si	P	Ti	Mn	Fe
smth mt lake_27um_14-15cm_pt1	±0.12	±0.19		±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.03	±0.10
smth mt lake_27um_14-15cm_pt2		±0.15	±0.00	±0.01	±0.02			±0.05	±0.16

Atom %

	C	O	F	Al	Si	P	Ti	Mn	Fe
smth mt lake_27um_14-15cm_pt1	42.44	43.92		0.13	0.08	0.02	0.05	0.12	13.25
smth mt lake_27um_14-15cm_pt2		58.51	0.00	0.35	0.28			0.33	40.52

Supplementary Fig S15. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1 and 2).

Image Name: Base(3)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.07 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 25.0 kV
 Magnification: 11419

Full scale counts: 6945
 Integral Counts: 1760871

Base(3)_pt3

Weight %

	O	F	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	Cl	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn
Base(3)_pt1	28.34	15.72		0.20	4.01	4.32	0.22	0.57		0.14	0.10	0.42			45.96	
Base(3)_pt2	21.66	0.00	0.00	1.21	7.94	8.99	0.86	0.22	0.08	0.38	0.14	0.71	0.17	1.92	54.64	1.09
Base(3)_pt3	28.70	1.33			0.32	0.18					0.05	0.03		0.31	69.08	

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	F	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	Cl	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn
Base(3)_pt1	±0.17	±0.16		±0.02	±0.04	±0.02	±0.01	±0.02		±0.01	±0.01	±0.03			±0.14	
Base(3)_pt2	±0.21	±0.00	±0.00	±0.04	±0.06	±0.04	±0.02	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02	±0.01	±0.03	±0.02	±0.07	±0.17	±0.09
Base(3)_pt3	±0.15	±0.16			±0.01	±0.02					±0.01	±0.01		±0.02	±0.16	

Atom %

	O	F	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	Cl	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn
Base(3)_pt1	46.96	21.94		0.22	3.94	4.07	0.19	0.47		0.09	0.06	0.23			21.82	
Base(3)_pt2	43.44	0.00	0.00	1.59	9.44	10.28	0.89	0.22	0.08	0.31	0.11	0.48	0.10	1.12	31.40	0.54
Base(3)_pt3	57.37	2.24			0.38	0.21					0.04	0.02		0.18	39.56	

Supplementary Fig S16. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1-3).

Image Name: Base(4)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.03 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 25.0 kV
 Magnification: 26104

Weight %

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	Mn	Fe
Base(4)_pt1	9.35	0.27	0.10	0.51	0.81	0.09	0.10	0.06	0.07	0.50	0.60	87.53

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	Mn	Fe
Base(4)_pt1	±0.07	±0.04	±0.02	±0.02	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.03	±0.07	±0.22

Atom %

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	Mn	Fe
Base(4)_pt1	26.02	0.53	0.19	0.85	1.29	0.13	0.14	0.06	0.08	0.47	0.48	69.77

Supplementary Fig S17. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an iron-rich and oxygen-depleted microspherule from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: smith mt lake_14-15cm_23um_site 2(2)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.25 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 25.0 kV
 Magnification: 3263

Weight %

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn	Mo
smith mt lake_14-15cm_23um_site 2(2)_pt1	9.41	0.22	0.94	2.32	0.55	0.35	0.15	1.14	84.45	0.48	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_23um_site 2(2)_pt2	4.60		0.48	0.61			0.06	1.12	92.32	0.28	0.52

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn	Mo
smith mt lake_14-15cm_23um_site 2(2)_pt1	±0.1 2	±0.0 3	±0.0 3	±0.0 3	±0.0 1	±0.0 2	±0.0 1	±0.0 5	±0.1 9	±0.0 4	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_23um_site 2(2)_pt2	±0.1 2		±0.0 3	±0.0 3			±0.0 1	±0.0 6	±0.2 0	±0.0 4	±0.0 4

Atom %

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	Cr	Mn	Fe	Zn	Mo
smith mt lake_14-15cm_23um_site 2(2)_pt1	25.72	0.39	1.52	3.61	0.77	0.48	0.13	0.91	66.15	0.32	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_23um_site 2(2)_pt2	14.30		0.88	1.09			0.06	1.01	82.17	0.21	0.27

Supplementary Fig S18. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for highly oxygen-depleted Fe grains from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1 and 2). Note that EDS Point 2 is a particle attached to a microspherule.

Metallic Dust Particles (MDPs)

Supplementary Fig S19. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a highly oxygen-depleted Fe metallic dust particle (MDP) from 44PY152 (11-12 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1-4).

Supplementary Fig S20. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a closeup section of a highly oxygen-depleted Fe metallic dust particle (MDP) (shown in Supplementary Fig S19) from 44PY152 (11-12 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1-5).

Image Name: 11-12c
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.50 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 15.0 kV
 Magnification: 1630

Weight %

	C-K	O-K	Na-K	Mg-K	Al-K	Si-K	P-K	K-K	Ti-K	Cr-K	Fe-K
11-12c_pt1	8.68	3.51	0.32	0.10	0.26	1.29	0.10	0.06	0.46	9.88	75.34

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	C-K	O-K	Na-K	Mg-K	Al-K	Si-K	P-K	K-K	Ti-K	Cr-K	Fe-K
11-12c_pt1	±0.05	±0.20	±0.03	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02	±0.10	±0.31

Atom %

	C-K	O-K	Na-K	Mg-K	Al-K	Si-K	P-K	K-K	Ti-K	Cr-K	Fe-K
11-12c_pt1	28.12	8.55	0.55	0.17	0.37	1.80	0.13	0.06	0.38	7.39	52.51

Atom % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	C-K	O-K	Na-K	Mg-K	Al-K	Si-K	P-K	K-K	Ti-K	Cr-K	Fe-K
11-12c_pt1	±0.16	±0.49	±0.05	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02	±0.07	±0.21

Supplementary Fig S21. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a chromferide (CrFe) metallic dust particle (MDP) from 44PY152 (11-12 cmbd), showing major element composition (Point 1).

Image Name: 14-15 deep_01
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.25 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 15.0 kV
 Magnification: 3263

Weight %	O-K	Mg-K	Al-K	Si-K	P-K	S-K	Cl-K	K-K	Ca-K	Ti-K	Cr-K	Mn-K	Fe-K	Ni-K	Zn-K
14-15 deep_01_pt1	2.91	0.08	0.32	1.21	0.09		0.01	0.05		0.71	15.11	1.57	71.95	5.99	
14-15 deep_01_pt2	10.39		0.43	1.57	0.11	0.33	0.00	0.10	0.12	0.80	0.41	2.04	83.70		
14-15 deep_01_pt3	24.01		0.57	1.92	0.26	0.23	0.05	0.14		1.26	0.52	0.73	70.29		
14-15 deep_01_pt4	27.20		0.31	1.80	0.85	2.96	0.22	0.24	0.10	0.86	3.44	0.80	51.94	1.09	8.17

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)	O-K	Mg-K	Al-K	Si-K	P-K	S-K	Cl-K	K-K	Ca-K	Ti-K	Cr-K	Mn-K	Fe-K	Ni-K	Zn-K
14-15 deep_01_pt1	±0.08	±0.02	±0.01	±0.02	±0.01		±0.01	±0.02		±0.03	±0.13	±0.09	±0.34	±0.26	
14-15 deep_01_pt2	±0.11		±0.03	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.03	±0.04	±0.07	±0.36		
14-15 deep_01_pt3	±0.40		±0.03	±0.04	±0.04	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02		±0.07	±0.04	±0.08	±0.39		
14-15 deep_01_pt4	±0.15		±0.03	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.05	±0.09	±0.14	±0.29	±0.10	±0.39

Atom %	O-K	Mg-K	Al-K	Si-K	P-K	S-K	Cl-K	K-K	Ca-K	Ti-K	Cr-K	Mn-K	Fe-K	Ni-K	Zn-K
14-15 deep_01_pt1	9.22	0.18	0.61	2.19	0.15		0.01	0.07		0.75	14.76	1.45	65.43	5.18	
14-15 deep_01_pt2	28.23		0.69	2.43	0.16	0.45	0.01	0.11	0.13	0.73	0.35	1.61	65.13		
14-15 deep_01_pt3	51.41		0.73	2.34	0.29	0.25	0.05	0.12		0.90	0.34	0.46	43.11		
14-15 deep_01_pt4	55.15		0.37	2.08	0.89	2.99	0.21	0.20	0.08	0.58	2.15	0.47	30.17	0.60	4.06

Supplementary Fig S22. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a CrFeNi metallic dust particle (MDP) from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1-4).

Supplementary Fig S23. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a CrFeSn metallic dust particle (MDP) from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1-3).

Authigenic Low O₂ Fe grains

Supplementary Fig S24. Authigenic oxygen-depleted “filigree” grain from 44PY152 (14-15 cm).

Supplementary Fig S25. Authigenic oxygen-depleted “filigree” grain from 44PY152 (14-15 cm).

Image Name: smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.13 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 25.0 kV
 Magnification: 6526

Weight %

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt1	1.69	0.27	1.42	1.35	0.55	0.15	0.05	0.08	0.15	0.11	1.30	92.89
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt2	0.00		1.41	2.34	1.60	0.48	0.06	0.12	0.11	0.20	1.47	92.22
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt3	0.00	0.19	1.45	2.36	1.65	0.40		0.11	0.17	0.22	1.34	92.10

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt1	±0.41	±0.05	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.02	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.01	±0.06	±0.21
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt2	±0.00		±0.05	±0.04	±0.02	±0.03	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02	±0.02	±0.07	±0.23
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt3	±0.00	±0.04	±0.05	±0.03	±0.02	±0.03		±0.01	±0.03	±0.02	±0.07	±0.24

Atom %

	O	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	Cr	Mn	Fe
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt1	5.46	0.56	2.72	2.48	0.91	0.25	0.07	0.10	0.16	0.11	1.23	85.95
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt2	0.00		2.76	4.40	2.74	0.79	0.08	0.16	0.12	0.20	1.41	87.33
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(1)_pt3	0.00	0.42	2.83	4.44	2.81	0.65		0.15	0.19	0.22	1.28	87.00

Supplementary Fig S26. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a highly oxygen-depleted “filigree” metallic dust particle (MDP) from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1-3).

Image Name: smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)
 Image Resolution: 512 by 340
 Image Pixel Size: 0.17 μm
 Acc. Voltage: 25.0 kV
 Magnification: 4894

Full scale counts: 6564 smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt1
 Integral Counts: 1167691

Full scale counts: 6564 smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt2
 Integral Counts: 2170461

Weight %

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt1	9.27		0.17	0.87	0.99	0.08	0.15	0.06	0.06	0.16		0.27	1.30	85.30			1.1
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt2	0.00	0.92		0.78	0.88	0.13					0.07	16.85	1.75	70.52	7.73	0.30	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt3-No Data.																	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt4	10.02		0.34	1.12	1.87	0.86	8.14	0.06	0.05	0.56		0.47	1.57	59.10			15.1

Weight % Error (+/- 1 Sigma)

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt1	±0.06		±0.02	±0.03	±0.01	±0.01	±0.03	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02		±0.02	±0.06	±0.21			±0.0
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt2	±0.00	±0.06		±0.02	±0.04	±0.01					±0.01	±0.06	±0.07	±0.17	±0.10	±0.04	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt3-No Data.																	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt4	±0.10		±0.03	±0.02	±0.02	±0.03	±0.05	±0.01	±0.01	±0.02		±0.02	±0.06	±0.17			±0.1

Atom %

	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt1	25.83		0.32	1.44	1.56	0.11	0.21	0.06	0.06	0.15		0.23	1.06	68.09			0.1
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt2	0.00	2.15		1.55	1.69	0.23					0.07	17.41	1.71	67.84	7.07	0.25	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt3-No Data.																	
smith mt lake_14-15cm_near 23um_iron bleb(3)_pt4	26.29		0.59	1.75	2.79	1.17	10.65	0.06	0.05	0.49		0.38	1.20	44.41			10.1

Supplementary Fig S27. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a highly oxygen-depleted “filigree” Fe (Point 1), CrFeNi (Point 2), and FeZn (Point 3) metallic dust particle (MDP) from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd), showing major element composition (Points 1-3).

Supplementary Fig S28. Optical microscope image of magnetic grains and oxidized grains with “filigree” material from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd).

Supplementary Fig 29. Optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of oxidized grains with “filigree” material from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd).

Supplementary Fig S30. Optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of oxidized grains with “filigree” material from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd).

Supplementary Fig S31. Optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of oxidized grains with “filigree” material from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd). SEM image at bottom shows bright regions that are oxygen-depleted and darker areas that are oxygen-rich.

44_PY_152_14_TO_15cm (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

Supplementary Fig S32. XRD data of “filigree” Fe-rich grains from 44PY152.

Granulometry

Supplementary Fig S33. Laser granulometry data for 44PY152 (N98, E24) showing sand fraction and silt and clay percentages. See Supplementary Table S2.

Supplementary Fig S34. Laser granulometry data for 44PY152 (N98, E24) showing statistical parameters using the Folk and Ward (Folk and Ward, 1957) method. See Supplementary Table S2.

Supplementary Fig S35. Cumulative granulometry data for 44PY152 (N98, E24) showing clay, silt, sand fractions, and microspherules/kg (see Supplementary Table S2).

Supplementary Fig S36. Laser granulometry data for 44PY152 with interpreted sediment stratigraphic zones (I-VII) (see Supplementary Table S2). The YDB layer with microspherule and PGE peaks is shown as a light brown band.

Supplementary Fig S37. Left panel, downcore abundance profiles of organic carbon (%OC - green symbols), total nitrogen (% TN – maroon), and soot carbon (SOOT % - black symbols). Right panel, the relative abundance of SOOT/TOC (%). Periodic enrichments in SOOT/TOC suggest a greater abundance of distal wildfires which may be coincident with periods of synoptic drought.

Supplementary Fig S38. Downcore profiles of sedimentary organic matter composition using stable isotopic signature of bulk organic carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{OC}}$ - green symbols) and carbon to nitrogen molar ratios (C:N - blue symbols). The composition of bulk soot via its stable isotopic signature ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{SOOT}}$ - black symbols) is also depicted. Invariant and depleted downcore $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{OC}}$ compared to erratic and large shifts in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{SOOT}}$ suggest soot deposited at the site did not result from pyrolysis of regional material and was likely transported from remote and distal pyrolysis events.

Supplementary Fig S39. Mercury (Hg) data for 44PY152 (N98 W24) showing Hg (ng/g) and Hg normalized to total organic carbon (Hg/TOC).

Supplementary Fig S40. Example of diagnostic projectile points recovered from 44PY152 or nearby sites (both *in-situ* and displaced context).

Bayesian Coding

Smith Mountain P_Sequence

Options()

{

Resolution=5;

Curve="IntCal20";

};

Plot()

{

Outlier_Model("General",Exp(1,-10,3),U(0,4),"t");

P_Sequence("Smith Mtn.",0.8,10)

{

Boundary();

R_Date("Beta-661185",11310,40){z=497.22;Outlier("General",1)};;

C_Date("Pt/MSp/NPs peak",(1950-12785),50){z=497.240;Outlier();color="green"};;

//Pt/MSp/NPs date shown for information only; not part of calculations

R_Date("UGA-64265",10650,30){z=497.240;Outlier("General",1)};;

R_Date("221026c-2",10690,110){z=497.270;Outlier("General",1)};;

R_Date("Beta-624542",10300,30){z=497.338;Outlier("General",1)};;

R_Date("UGA-69329",8930,30){z=497.362;Outlier("General",1)};;

C_Date("E. Archaic Point",(1950-9450),450){z=497.4075;Outlier("General",1);color="orange"};;

R_Date("Beta-456850",8209,24){z=497.452;Outlier("General",1)};;

Boundary();

};

};

Note: The Pt/MSp/NPs peak was included in the OxCal code as a queried calendar date for comparison with the modeled age-depth sequence, rather than as a standard radiocarbon constraint.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1. Bayesian age–depth model results generated in OxCal v4.4 for the Smith Mountain sequence. Unmodeled and modeled radiocarbon ages (in years BP) are shown with associated 1σ uncertainties (σ) and 68.3% and 95.4% probability ranges. Agreement indices (A_{model} , A_{overall} , and individual A values) indicate good overall model performance. The red box highlights the radiocarbon determination (R_Date UGA-64265) that anchors the modeled interval corresponding to the inferred Younger Dryas Boundary (YDB) layer. Also shown is a labeled comparison to the canonical YDB age range reported by Kennett et al. ($12,785 \pm 50$ cal BP). This age is included strictly as an informational reference label and was not incorporated into the Bayesian model calculations or used as a constraint.

Name	Unmodelled (BP)						Modelled (BP)						Indices						
	μ	σ	from_68.3	to_68.3	from_95.4	to_95.4	μ	σ	from_68.3	to_68.3	from_95.4	to_95.4	$A_{\text{model}}=111.2$	$A_{\text{overall}}=109.7$	A_{comb}	A	L	P	C
Depth_Model																			
Page																			
Boundary							9209	88	9293	9105	9401	9032							99.4
R_Date Beta-456850	9165	72	9260	9035	9280	9027	9209	88	9293	9105	9401	9032			98.7				99.4
C_Date E. Archaic Point	9451	450	9902	9000	10351	8551	9484	375	10070	9041	10229	9029			105.2				69.3
R_Date UGA-69329	10059	86	10185	9960	10196	9909	10082	98	10198	9962	10258	9913			98.2				99.5
R_Date Beta-624542	12089	148	12421	11942	12450	11886	12166	179	12449	11953	12526	11936			92				99.8
R_Date 221026c-2	12648	123	12752	12505	12890	12204	12707	73	12752	12634	12886	12515			134.7				99.5
R_Date UGA-64265	12680	35	12720	12630	12727	12621	12720	55	12759	12671	12851	12624			104.1				99.9
C_Date Pt/MSp/NPs peak	12785	50	12837	12734	12886	12686	12786	50	12836	12736	12886	12685					82.5		99.9
R_Date Beta-661185	13203	48	13241	13124	13300	13116	13229	67	13296	13135	13370	13110			98.7				99.9
Boundary							13229	67	13296	13135	13370	13110							99.9
▲ P_Sequence Smith Mtn.																			
U(0.4)	2	1.1431	3.98986e-17	4	3.98986e-17	4	0.927358	0.550298	5.37764e-17	1.26	5.37764e-17	1.828			100				99.3
Exp(1,-10.3)	1.93362	0.999125	1.726	2.935	-0.211	2.935	1.9363	0.987048											100
▲ Outlier_Model General							34	48	-4	46	-15	172							100

Supplementary Table S2. Laser granulometry of sediments from 44PY152 (N98, E24).

Depth (range)	Midpoint	Gravel %	Sand %	Mud %	Mean ¹	Sorting ¹	Skewness ¹	Kurtosis ¹	% MEDIUM SAND:	% FINE SAND:	% V FINE SAND:	% V COARSE SILT:	% COARSE SILT:	% MEDIUM SILT:	% FINE SILT:	% V FINE SILT:	% CLAY:
0-1	0.5	0.00	24.21	75.79	5.64	2.06	0.10	0.91	0.25	7.66	16.30	16.88	16.82	17.42	10.38	7.83	6.46
1-2	1.5	0.00	24.64	75.36	5.60	2.08	0.07	0.92	1.04	8.56	15.04	16.80	16.53	17.65	10.54	7.77	6.07
2-3	2.5	0.00	26.55	73.45	5.51	2.10	0.07	0.92	1.40	9.53	15.63	16.59	16.16	17.27	10.11	7.36	5.96
3-4	3.5	0.00	19.43	80.57	5.88	2.03	0.05	0.93	0.25	5.85	13.33	16.41	17.18	19.36	11.78	8.77	7.07
4-5	4.5	0.00	20.77	79.23	5.81	2.03	0.05	0.91	0.22	6.42	14.12	16.48	17.08	18.86	11.64	8.61	6.57
5-6	5.5	0.00	24.44	75.56	5.66	2.08	0.07	0.89	0.31	8.23	15.90	16.35	15.83	17.71	11.09	8.20	6.37
6-7	6.5	0.00	24.00	76.00	5.63	2.02	0.03	0.90	1.23	8.28	14.49	17.64	15.39	18.22	11.69	8.02	5.04
7-8	7.5	0.00	23.80	76.20	5.63	2.06	0.05	0.92	1.17	8.34	14.29	17.11	16.31	18.06	11.04	7.89	5.79
8-9	8.5	0.00	24.34	75.66	5.67	2.13	0.05	0.91	1.20	8.67	14.47	15.97	15.94	17.60	11.29	8.19	6.66
9-10	9.5	0.00	23.79	76.21	5.70	2.12	0.03	0.91	1.31	8.75	13.73	15.85	15.82	18.20	11.43	8.47	6.44
10-11	10.5	0.00	25.65	74.35	5.63	2.15	0.04	0.89	1.47	8.98	15.20	14.76	15.77	17.75	11.28	8.32	6.46
11-12	11.5	0.00	29.03	70.97	5.60	2.30	-0.04	0.83	2.86	11.61	14.56	9.76	15.27	18.71	11.73	8.42	7.08
12-13	12.5	0.00	24.84	75.16	5.69	2.13	0.04	0.90	1.35	8.00	15.49	15.40	15.20	18.27	11.20	8.43	6.65
13-14	13.5	0.00	25.26	74.74	5.73	2.18	-0.01	0.88	1.52	8.86	14.88	13.74	14.39	18.91	12.10	8.56	7.03
14-15	14.5	0.00	23.32	76.68	5.85	2.21	0.05	0.88	0.99	7.26	15.07	14.33	15.09	17.76	11.73	9.11	8.65
15-16	15.5	0.00	22.50	77.50	5.90	2.20	-0.03	0.86	1.23	7.93	13.34	13.47	14.06	18.55	13.35	10.42	7.65
16-17	16.5	0.00	25.92	74.08	5.67	2.19	0.05	0.89	1.48	8.96	15.47	14.96	14.88	17.69	11.03	8.47	7.06
17-18	17.5	0.00	25.49	74.51	5.65	2.16	0.05	0.90	2.30	7.65	15.54	14.94	15.82	17.02	11.78	8.12	6.82
18-19	18.5	0.00	26.82	73.18	5.60	2.18	0.07	0.91	1.92	8.90	16.01	16.08	14.21	17.36	10.65	8.07	6.81
19-20	19.5	0.00	20.39	79.61	5.89	2.09	-0.02	0.93	1.13	6.89	12.37	14.11	16.25	20.48	12.72	9.11	6.94
20-21	20.5	0.00	26.31	73.69	5.63	2.19	0.06	0.91	1.91	9.19	15.20	16.18	13.91	17.34	11.10	8.04	7.11
21-22	21.5	0.00	25.70	74.30	5.67	2.16	0.03	0.88	1.55	8.84	15.31	15.13	14.73	17.76	11.44	8.64	6.60
22-23	22.5	0.00	23.82	76.18	5.74	2.15	0.05	0.91	1.26	7.64	14.91	15.77	15.40	18.07	11.21	8.54	7.19
23-24	23.5	0.00	24.99	75.01	5.69	2.14	0.01	0.88	1.38	8.57	15.03	14.47	15.28	18.36	11.94	8.58	6.38
24-25	24.5	0.00	23.87	76.13	5.79	2.17	-0.01	0.88	1.58	8.29	13.99	14.13	14.58	18.74	12.43	9.41	6.84
25-26	25.5	0.00	25.92	74.08	5.66	2.16	0.04	0.88	1.41	9.01	15.50	15.24	14.75	17.49	11.41	8.56	6.63
26-27	26.5	0.00	24.47	75.53	5.67	2.09	0.03	0.89	1.24	8.11	15.12	16.17	14.93	18.34	11.67	8.37	6.04

¹Grainsize statistics calculated using the Folk and Ward method in Φ units.

Supplementary Table S3. Mass corrected magnetic susceptibility ($10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$).

Box	¹ Depth (cmbd)	samp_wt (g)	density (g/cm ³)	MS2B meter (10 ⁻⁵ SI)	K (Vol. Sus.) (10 ⁻⁶ SI)	Kfd% (Pct.)	X Mass Specific Sus, 10 ⁻⁶ m ³ kg ⁻¹
1.00	0.50	15.40	2.20	94.85	13.56	10.07	6.16
2.00	1.50	15.32	2.19	87.05	12.45	10.22	5.68
3.00	2.50	14.96	2.14	88.35	12.63	10.30	5.91
4.00	3.50	15.94	2.28	92.60	13.24	10.58	5.81
5.00	4.50	14.22	2.03	82.45	11.79	10.13	5.80
6.00	5.50	15.60	2.23	86.70	12.40	10.15	5.56
7.00	6.50	15.49	2.21	80.95	11.58	10.01	5.22
8.00	7.50	16.13	2.30	82.45	11.79	9.70	5.11
9.00	8.50	15.50	2.21	78.45	11.22	10.13	5.06
10.00	9.50	15.06	2.15	75.60	10.81	9.66	5.02
11.00	10.50	14.83	2.12	81.05	11.59	9.13	5.47
12.00	11.50	15.31	2.19	72.80	10.41	10.37	4.75
13.00	12.50	14.80	2.11	67.45	9.65	10.16	4.56
14.00	13.50	14.75	2.11	63.85	9.13	10.10	4.33
15.00	14.50	14.89	2.13	66.80	9.55	10.18	4.49
16.00	15.50	14.83	2.12	66.70	9.54	9.60	4.50
17.00	16.50	14.90	2.13	64.10	9.17	10.45	4.30
18.00	17.50	15.01	2.14	66.00	9.44	10.91	4.40
19.00	18.50	15.53	2.22	66.50	9.51	9.92	4.28
20.00	19.50	14.88	2.13	64.45	9.22	10.63	4.33
21.00	20.50	14.67	2.10	59.35	8.49	9.77	4.05
22.00	21.50	14.57	2.08	58.75	8.40	10.21	4.03
23.00	22.50	15.37	2.20	62.95	9.00	10.09	4.10
24.00	23.50	14.62	2.09	58.90	8.42	10.36	4.03
25.00	24.50	14.66	2.09	60.25	8.62	10.62	4.11
26.00	25.50	13.02	1.86	52.30	7.48	9.46	4.02
27.00	26.50	15.08	2.15	60.70	8.68	10.13	4.03

¹cmbd=centimeters below datum (not depth below surface).

Supplementary Table S4. Smith Mountain Lake (44PY152) SP-TOF-ICPMS nanoparticle data.

<https://zenodo.org/records/13947879>

Supplementary Table S5. Laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) for microspherules from 44PY152 (14-15 cmbd). Data is given in parts per million (ppm).

Element	Spherule 1	Spherule 2	Spherule 3	Spherule 4	Spherule 5	Spherule 6	Spherule 7	Spherule 8	^a DL (ppm)
Na	6303	3843			1070	854	3981	2519	760
Mg	1023	301							52
Al									29746
Si	2699	7063	11367	17725	2816	8598	5670	4009	33
Ca	13164	8055	2098	4601	4054	bdl	6597	737	82
Sc									3
Ti	400						426		210
V	17	6	2	7	8	26	40	10	2
Cr	2071	191	136	1416	896	1760	304	404	19
Mn	8227	3462	7383	6756	636	11268	4628	4964	4
Fe	990000	990000	990000	990000	990000	990000	985000	990000	115
Co	167	150	73	193	69	45	55	53	20
Ni	1627	417	195	1724	856	131	52	85	4
Cu	855	166	27	675	3063	1413	256	479	5
Zn	46	193	57	58	387		220	132	1
Rb	2.66								1.44
Sr	44.50	8.53			10.77		8.04	8.82	4.63
Y		0.07			1.78		0.40	0.49	0.07
Zr	0.57	0.63	0.63		1.73	0.58	0.92	2.69	0.05
Nb	1.69	0.09	0.54	0.80	0.74	174.83	11.81	0.59	0.02
Mo	324.16	21.12	65.69	406.30	331.66	113.13	35.52	34.78	0.27
Ba		5.46			5.10		7.09	13.10	0.63
La		0.21	0.09		0.76		0.07	0.45	0.03
Ce	0.03	0.16	0.15	0.15	1.63	0.05	0.23	1.14	0.01
Nd		0.07		0.68	0.98			0.63	0.05
Sm			0.16	0.38	0.36			0.13	0.12
Gd	0.76		0.88	0.59				0.67	0.43
Dy					0.17		0.12	0.32	0.08
Er	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.41	0.14				0.06
Yb				0.52	0.10	0.08		0.10	0.07
Hf									0.05
Re									0.02
Pt	0.27	1.25	0.27	0.66	0.04	0.12	1.29	0.69	0.03
Pb	0.38	1.53	0.34	1.14	593.33	0.20	2.17	0.09	0.03
Th		0.02	0.01	0.08	0.67		0.05	0.37	0.00
U	0.02	0.04	0.01		0.20	0.00	0.01	0.11	0.00

^aDL= Detection limits (3 standard deviations of the blanks).

No data= Below detection limit.

Supplementary Table S6. Organic carbon and Soot carbon for 44PY152 samples.

Depth in Sediment (cm)	OC (%)	TN (%)	SOOT (%)		SOOT/OC (%)		C:N (mol:mol)	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{OC}}$ ‰	$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{TN}}$ ‰	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{SOOT}}$ ‰			
0-1	0.22	--	0.03	0.06	0.01	27.25	--	10.2	-23.6	--	6.6	-18.3	0.6
1-2	0.23	--	0.03	--	--	--	--	9.9	-23.5	--	6.1	--	--
2-3	0.20	--	0.02	0.07	0.01	32.72	--	10.0	-23.5	--	6.1	-18.6	0.1
3-4	0.22	--	0.03	--	--	--	--	10.5	-23.5	--	6.1	--	--
4-5	0.24	--	0.03	0.08	0.01	31.14	--	9.3	-23.9	--	5.8	-17.7	0.1
5-6	0.21	--	0.03	--	--	--	--	9.0	-23.3	--	6.4	--	--
6-7	0.21	--	0.03	0.07	--	34.09	--	9.3	-23.3	--	6.6	-19.5	1.0
7-8	0.20	--	0.03	0.07	0.01	33.56	--	9.0	-23.4	--	6.3	-18.2	0.7
8-9	0.21	--	0.03	0.06	0.01	29.21	--	9.6	-23.2	--	5.7	-17.7	1.3
9-10	0.23	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.00	26.06	4.36	7.8	-23.2	0.0	6.0	-14.7	2.3
10-11	0.18	--	0.03	0.06	0.00	34.92	--	7.6	-23.1	--	6.3	-19.0	1.4
11-12	0.18	--	0.03	0.06	0.00	31.77	--	7.6	-23.0	--	6.2	-16.9	0.5
12-13	0.20	--	0.03	0.06	0.01	33.04	--	7.5	-23.4	--	6.7	-18.4	1.3
13-14	0.18	0.02	0.03	0.06	0.01	30.15	8.20	7.4	-23.3	0.3	6.5	-19.2	1.1
14-15	0.19	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.01	29.52	4.56	7.8	-22.9	0.1	6.3	-20.0	2.3
15-16	0.18	0.02	0.03	0.04	--	19.57	--	7.4	-22.9	0.2	6.4	-20.6	--
16-17	0.17	0.03	0.03	0.04	--	21.74	--	8.1	-23.0	0.3	6.4	-21.0	--
17-18	0.20	--	0.03	0.06	0.00	29.79	--	6.6	-23.8	--	6.3	-16.1	1.2
18-19	0.18	--	0.03	--	--	--	--	7.4	-23.4	--	6.4	--	--
19-20	0.20	--	0.03	--	--	--	--	6.3	-23.2	--	6.2	--	--
20-21	0.18	--	0.03	0.06	0.00	35.96	--	6.1	-23.2	--	6.0	-18.0	0.5
21-22	0.17	--	0.03	--	--	--	--	6.4	-23.1	--	6.4	--	--
22-23	0.18	--	0.03	--	--	--	--	5.7	-23.2	--	6.4	--	--
23-24	0.19	--	0.04	0.07	0.01	36.03	--	5.8	-22.9	--	6.3	-18.3	1.2
24-25	0.20	--	0.04	--	--	--	--	5.7	-22.9	--	6.6	--	--
25-26	0.18	--	0.04	--	--	--	--	6.5	-22.6	--	6.3	--	--
26-27	0.19	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.01	29.73	4.45	--	-23.0	0.0	6.2	-17.6	2.1

Supplementary Table S7. Carbon and nitrogen stable isotopes and mercury (Hg) from bulk sediments.

Sample ID	Sample #	Depth (cm)	Sample Mass (mg)	Carbon Content (mg)	Carbon Content (%)	Corrected $\delta^{13}C$	Nitrogen Content (mg)	Nitrogen Content (%)	Corrected $\delta^{15}N$	Hg (ng/g)	Hg/TOC	C/N Ratio
0	#1 0 TO 1 cm	0.5	73.0	0.2	0.2	-23.6	0.02	0.03	6.6	30.4	138.0	7.9
1	#2 1 TO 2 cm	1.5	68.6	0.2	0.2	-23.5	0.02	0.03	6.1	25.6	110.4	8.8
2	#3 2 TO 3 cm	2.5	71.2	0.1	0.2	-23.5	0.02	0.02	6.1	21.2	103.7	8.5
3	#4 3 TO 4 cm	3.5	69.2	0.2	0.2	-23.5	0.02	0.03	6.1	25.5	116.0	8.6
4	#5 4 TO 5 cm	4.5	63.4	0.2	0.2	-23.9	0.02	0.03	5.8	23.4	97.0	9.0
5	#6 5 TO 6 cm	5.5	65.1	0.1	0.2	-23.3	0.02	0.03	6.4	21.2	102.4	8.0
6	#7 6 TO 7 cm	6.5	70.9	0.1	0.2	-23.3	0.02	0.03	6.6	22.0	107.2	7.7
7	#8 7 TO 8 cm	7.5	79.8	0.2	0.2	-23.4	0.02	0.03	6.3	23.2	116.4	8.0
8	#9 8 TO 9 cm	8.5	74.2	0.2	0.2	-23.2	0.02	0.03	5.7	27.4	132.5	7.7
9	#10 9 TO 10 cm	9.5	72.4	0.1	0.2	-23.2	0.02	0.03	6.0	24.2	120.8	7.3
10	#11 10 TO 11 cm	10.5	75.8	0.1	0.2	-23.1	0.02	0.03	6.3	26.5	149.1	6.7
11	#12 11 TO 12 cm	11.5	71.0	0.1	0.2	-23.0	0.02	0.03	6.2	29.2	159.7	6.5
12	#13 12 TO 13 cm	12.5	75.1	0.1	0.2	-23.4	0.02	0.03	6.7	26.1	132.7	6.5
13	#14 13 TO 14 cm	13.5	75.9	0.1	0.2	-23.0	0.02	0.03	6.5	26.7	157.6	5.9
14	#15 14 TO 15 cm	14.5	76.4	0.1	0.2	-23.1	0.02	0.03	6.3	25.9	145.5	6.0
15	#16 15 TO 16 cm	15.5	77.0	0.1	0.2	-23.1	0.02	0.03	6.4	30.1	179.4	6.3
16	#17 16 TO 17 cm	16.5	72.5	0.1	0.2	-23.3	0.02	0.03	6.4	32.7	217.4	5.6
17	#18 17 TO 18 cm	17.5	79.4	0.2	0.2	-23.8	0.02	0.03	6.3	25.1	125.8	6.9
18	#19 18 TO 19 cm	18.5	73.4	0.1	0.2	-23.4	0.02	0.03	6.4	29.9	167.8	5.7
19	#20 19 TO 20 cm	19.5	73.9	0.1	0.2	-23.2	0.02	0.03	6.2	32.9	163.1	6.4
20	#21 20 TO 21 cm	20.5	68.9	0.1	0.2	-23.2	0.02	0.03	6.0	27.5	157.1	5.4
21	#22 21 TO 22 cm	21.5	79.9	0.1	0.2	-23.1	0.03	0.03	6.4	31.4	184.9	5.2
22	#23 22 TO 23 cm	22.5	70.7	0.1	0.2	-23.2	0.02	0.03	6.4	33.8	183.2	5.5
23	#24 23 TO 24 cm	23.5	77.2	0.1	0.2	-22.9	0.03	0.04	6.3	34.9	184.7	4.9
24	#25 24 TO 25 cm	24.5	71.5	0.1	0.2	-22.9	0.03	0.04	6.6	35.0	176.4	4.9
25	#26 25 TO 26 cm	25.5	79.2	0.1	0.2	-22.6	0.03	0.04	6.3	35.0	199.1	4.9
26	#27 26 TO 27 cm	26.5	73.6	0.1	0.2	-23.0	0.03	0.04	6.2	38.1	214.6	5.1

USGS 40 $\delta^{15}N$ Standard Deviation
 USGS 41a $\delta^{13}C$ Standard Deviation
 USGS 41a $\delta^{15}N$ Standard Deviation

Supplementary Table S8. Operating conditions for inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometer analysis (TOFWERK icpTOF R).

Instrument parameter	Value				
Plasma Power	1550 V				
Nebulizer Gas Flow	1.1-1.14 L/min				
Auxiliary Gas Flow	0.8 L/min				
Cooling Gas Flow	14 L/min				
Injector Diameter	2.5 mm				
Collision Cell Gas	5 mL/min He with 4.5% H ₂				
CCT Bias	-2.50 V				
Notch	Mass	29	32	36.3	41
	Amplitude (V)	1.6	2.0	2.0	1.2
Data acquisition	Continuous Mode				
Detected Mass Range	14-275 m/Z				
TOF Repetition Rate	33 kHz				
TOF Time Resolution	30 μs				
Integration Time	2 ms				
Sample Flow Rate	0.455 mL/min				
Transport Efficiency	6.6%				
(CeO/Ce)	< 3.0%				

Supplementary Table S9. Elements were monitored for single particle-inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometer analysis and the corresponding particle mass and size detection limits.

Element	Isotope	Mass detection limit (g)	Size detection limit (nm, assuming pure metallic particle)	Size detection limit (nm, assuming pure metal oxide particle)	Metal oxide form
Al	²⁷ Al	6.90×10^{-15}	170	185	Al ₂ O ₃
Ti	⁴⁸ Ti	7.19×10^{-16}	67	82	TiO ₂
V	⁵¹ V	4.20×10^{-16}	51	75	V ₂ O ₅
Cr	⁵² Cr	3.27×10^{-16}	44	56	Cr ₂ O ₃
Mn	⁵⁵ Mn	2.48×10^{-16}	40	53	MnO ₂
Fe	⁵⁶ Fe	8.88×10^{-16}	60	77	Fe ₂ O ₃
Co	⁵⁹ Co	1.99×10^{-16}	35	44	Co ₃ O ₄
Ni	⁶⁰ Ni	8.64×10^{-16}	57	68	NiO
Cu	⁶⁵ Cu	6.66×10^{-16}	52	63	CuO
Zn	⁶⁶ Zn	1.50×10^{-15}	74	86	ZnO
As	⁷⁵ As	1.55×10^{-15}	80	101	As ₂ O ₃

Zr	⁹⁰ Zr	3.29×10^{-16}	46	53	ZrO ₂
Nb	⁹³ Nb	1.56×10^{-16}	33	44	Nb ₂ O ₅
Ru	¹⁰² Ru	4.16×10^{-16}	48	53	RuO ₂
Rh	¹⁰³ Rh	9.51×10^{-17}	30	35	Rh ₂ O ₃
Pd	¹⁰⁶ Pd	5.45×10^{-16}	67	59	PdO
Sn	¹²⁰ Sn	3.25×10^{-16}	44	48	SnO ₂
Sb	¹²¹ Sb	2.61×10^{-16}	42	49	Sb ₂ O ₃
Ba	¹³⁸ Ba	9.50×10^{-17}	37	33	BaO
La	¹³⁹ La	7.29×10^{-17}	28	29	La ₂ O ₃
Ce	¹⁴⁰ Ce	8.63×10^{-17}	29	30	CeO ₂
Pr	¹⁴¹ Pr	6.23×10^{-17}	26	28	Pr ₆ O ₁₁
Nd	¹⁴² Nd	1.70×10^{-16}	36	37	Nd ₂ O ₃
Sm	¹⁵² Sm	2.07×10^{-16}	38	38	Sm ₂ O ₃
Eu	¹⁵³ Eu	1.00×10^{-16}	33	31	Eu ₂ O ₃
Gd	¹⁵⁸ Gd	2.39×10^{-16}	39	41	Gd ₂ O ₃
Tb	¹⁵⁹ Tb	5.26×10^{-17}	23	25	Tb ₄ O ₇
Dy	¹⁶⁴ Dy	1.72×10^{-16}	34	36	Dy ₂ O ₃
Ho	¹⁶⁵ Ho	5.10×10^{-17}	22	24	Ho ₂ O ₃
Er	¹⁶⁶ Er	1.53×10^{-16}	32	34	Er ₂ O ₃
Tm	¹⁶⁹ Tm	5.15×10^{-17}	22	24	Tm ₂ O ₃
Yb	¹⁷⁴ Yb	1.57×10^{-16}	36	33	Yb ₂ O ₃
Lu	¹⁷⁵ Lu	4.38×10^{-17}	20	22	Lu ₂ O ₃
Hf	¹⁸⁰ Hf	1.95×10^{-16}	30	36	HfO ₂
Ta	¹⁸¹ Ta	1.78×10^{-16}	33	42	Ta ₂ O ₅
W	¹⁸⁴ W	3.55×10^{-16}	27	37	WO ₂
Re	¹⁸⁷ Re	1.04×10^{-16}	26	29	ReO ₂
Os	¹⁹² Os	1.20×10^{-16}	27	30	OsO ₂
Ir	¹⁹³ Ir	1.54×10^{-16}	25	32	IrO ₂
Pt	¹⁹⁵ Pt	4.09×10^{-16}	41	45	PtO ₂
Au	¹⁹⁷ Au	2.09×10^{-16}	28	34	Au ₂ O ₃
Pb	²⁰⁸ Pb	1.19×10^{-16}	27	30	PbO
Th	²³² Th	7.64×10^{-17}	23	26	ThO ₂
U	²³⁸ U	6.82×10^{-17}	19	24	UO ₂

The particle mass detection limit is calculated according to the Poisson distribution =

$$Mass_{detection\ limit} = 3.29\sqrt{background\ signal} + 2.71$$

The size detection limit is calculated as the equivalent spherical diameter from the particle mass detection limit, assuming pure metal and metal oxide phases.

Supplementary Table S10. USGS Reference material BIR-1G data and detection limits.

	BIR1-G average			RSD	Reference values (GEOREM)	% deviation from Lit	Detection limits
	units	(n=7)	STDEV				
Na2O wt%	wt%	1.9	0.06	3%	1.85	1%	0.0916
MgO wt%	wt%	9.7	0.43	4%	9.4	3%	0.0160
Al2O3 wt%	wt%	14.5	0.22	2%	15.5	-7%	0.0223
SiO2 wt%	wt%	48.3	0.56	1%	47.5	2%	7.7405
CaO wt%	wt%	12.1	0.56	5%	13.3	-9%	0.2339
Sc	ppm	39.0	0.62	2%	43	-9%	1.5966
TiO2 wt%	wt%	0.9	0.03	3%	1.04	-13%	0.0039
V	ppm	317.4	6.57	2%	326	-3%	0.6232
Cr	ppm	445.1	20.34	5%	392	14%	13.5434
MnO wt%	wt%	0.2	0.01	4%	0.19	-15%	0.0122
FeO wt%	wt%	10.4	0.24	2%	10.4	0%	0.0156
Co	ppm	53.0	1.99	4%	52	2%	0.6268
Ni	ppm	197.1	7.06	4%	178	11%	8.7188
Cu	ppm	144.6	6.52	5%	119	21%	0.9511
Zn	ppm	68.9	2.06	3%	78	-12%	3.4550
Rb	ppm	0.3	0.05	17%	0.197	33%	0.1189
Sr	ppm	107.4	3.90	4%	109	-1%	0.2367
Y	ppm	13.0	0.45	3%	14.3	-9%	0.0287
Zr	ppm	12.3	0.12	1%	14	-12%	1.7960
Nb	ppm	0.5	0.02	4%	0.52	-1%	0.0049
Mo	ppm	0.103	0.02	22%	0.075	37%	0.0402
Rh	ppm	0.005	0.00	77%	not reported		0.0036
Pd	ppm	0.060	0.03	45%	not reported		0.0458
Ba	ppm	6.608	0.15	2%	6.5	2%	1.2978
La	ppm	0.575	0.02	4%	0.609	-6%	0.0013
Ce	ppm	1.928	0.04	2%	1.89	2%	0.0012
Nd	ppm	2.259	0.10	5%	2.37	-5%	0.0061
Sm	ppm	1.061	0.10	9%	1.09	-3%	0.0406
Gd	ppm	1.632	0.07	4%	1.85	-12%	0.1237
Dy	ppm	2.232	0.08	4%	2.55	-12%	0.0031
Er	ppm	1.523	0.08	5%	1.7	-10%	0.0033
Yb	ppm	1.462	0.06	4%	1.64	-11%	0.0095
Hf	ppm	0.472	0.06	13%	0.57	-17%	0.0044
Re	ppm	0.001	0.00	77%	0.00053	143%	0.0007
Ir	ppm	0.006	0.00	76%	not reported		0.0018
Pt	ppm	0.904	0.07	7%	0.92	-2%	0.0022
Pb	ppm	3.655	0.23	6%	3.7	-1%	0.0159
Th	ppm	0.026	0.00	15%	0.03	-14%	0.0002
U	ppm	0.018	0.00	16%	0.023	-21%	0.0001

References

Folk, R.L., Ward, W.C., 1957. Brazos River bar [Texas]; a study in the significance of grain size parameters, *Journal of sedimentary research* 27, 3–26.